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Multi-Sensory Approach in Reading Difficulties of Grade 1 Pupils in Lagadlarin/ Olo-Olo Elementary School

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the reading difficulties of grade one pupils in Lagadlarin/ Olo-Olo Elementary School. It is intended to contribute in the body of knowledge about how to practice reading for children. Specifically, it targeted to determine the reading performance of the children and to identify their reading ability. The study used the quantitative method of research. The subject of this study was the 60 grade one pupils from Lagadlarin/ Olo-Olo Elementary School. The technique in analyzing data of this research was the descriptive technique.

Specifically, it sought answer to the following questions:

1. What are the reading performance of grade one pupils in the following skills:
 - 1.1 recognition of c-v-c words
 - 1.2 recognition of Dolch Basic Sight Words
 - 1.3 understanding words, phrases, and sentences?
2. How may the grade one pupils be characterized in terms of their reading ability, such as;
 - 2.1 word reader
 - 2.2 syllable reader
 - 2.3 non- reader
3. Is there significant relationship between the reading skills and reading ability of grade one pupils?
4. What learning activities may be proposed to enhance pupils' reading abilities?

In the context of the foregoing findings, the following conclusions are hereby drawn by the researcher.

1. The reading performance of grade one pupils is in the fair level.
2. The reading ability of the grade one pupils in English is syllable reader.
3. There is a significant relationship between the reading skills and reading ability of grade one pupils.
4. Proposed learning activities may help improve the reading skills and reading ability of the grade one pupils.

After going through the conclusions supported by the findings on the study, the researcher hereby presents the following recommendations.

1. Reading performance skills may stimulate pupils to join in a repeated reading of a book with memorable phrases or sound effects and added gestures.

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2. The proposed learning activities may be employed to allow pupils exhibit their understanding of readings in many ways. These activities will reassure them to make connections between reading passages and their knowledge.
3. The results of this study may be presented to the Public Schools District Supervisors and to the school heads for further comments before implementing the proposed learning activities by the Grade 1 teachers.
4. Similar studies may be recommended based on the results after the implementation of the proposed learning activities to enhance pupils' reading abilities.

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